

Influence and detectability of parasitic stars

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1. Introduction

One of my earlier notes (77-03-10) gives expressions for the maximum angular accuracy that can be attained with a telescope and modulating grid assuming diffraction-limited optics and Poisson-distributed counts. One of the conclusions was that a periodic grid designed to give maximum accuracy for observations of single stars will have such a small period (angle between centres of adjacent slits) that only the fundamental frequency of the grid is transferred to the light curve, which is then purely sinusoidal.

If there are parasitic stars within the cathod spot we get a displaced light curve (with a corresponding error in the position derived), an increased average intensity and a decreased degree of modulation. The chances of detecting a parasite from the deviations of the average intensity and modulation from predicted values are presumably not very good, because of varying cathod sensitivity and MTF over the field and the non-constant background flux. Without external information it is in any case impossible to correct the erroneous position even if the disturbance is detected.

With increased grid period the single-star light curve will contain higher-order Fourier components making it possible not only to detect but also to correct for the influence of parasites. This advantage is gained at the cost of some accuracy for single-star observations.

For a given aperture it is required that the grid is optimised, i.e. designed to give the best compromise between the two conflicting requirements: good accuracy for observations of single stars and good ability to detect and correct for non-negligible parasites. For the ideal instrument considered in this note there happens to be a rather obvious compromise, but the general case will require a more refined analysis than is given here.

The ideal instrument and detection procedure are described in Section 2, samples of numerical results are given in Section 3. An Appendix contains a mathematical formulation of the detection problem.

2.1. Description of instrument

The instrument is supposed to have a rectangular aperture with a full length $2a$ in the scanning direction. The size of the aperture in the perpendicular direction does not influence the instrument's resolving power but determines the light-gathering capacity and enters formally via the number of counted photons. The secondary mirror obstruction is rectangular with a linear size equal to half of the aperture size in any direction ($\alpha = \beta = 0.5$) and located symmetrically around the optical axis in the scanning direction (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The spectral bandwidth is about 200 nm centred at $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 425$ nm. Assuming diffraction-limited performance the resulting intensity distribution $J(p)$ for a star will be as shown in Fig. 1. The angle $206265'' \lambda_{\text{eff}}/2a$ may be considered as the width of the central diffraction peak. From here on, all angles will be given in units of this angle (resolution unit, RU), whereby equations and graphs become independent of the instrument's linear size ($2a$). However, sometimes absolute angles in arcsec are given as well, always referring then to a baseline version of the instrument with a $16 \times 8 \text{ cm}^2$ aperture, for which $1 \text{ RU} = 0''.548$.

But even if the mean errors are expressed in RU they depend also on the number of counted photons from the star under observation. We always assume that we have 3161δ counts from the main star (and negligible background counts). According to Table 1 in the MDS Report this corresponds to 1^{st} observation of a 9^{m} star with the baseline instrument.

The grid is defined by its period s and slit width r ($\delta = r/s < 1$). In the previous notes γ_{eff} denotes s expressed in RU. For each value of s there is a value of r which gives the least mean error for an observation of a single star. It is assumed that r is always chosen optimally in this respect, so that the grid is fully specified by the single parameter s .

Fig.1. Aperture shape and resulting Fraunhofer diffraction. $J(p)$ is the area-normalised light curve that would be obtained by scanning a stellar image with a very narrow slit oriented normally to the scanning direction. p is the angular distance in resolution units $(206265''\lambda_{\text{eff}}/2a)$ between the slit and image centre. p'' is the distance in arcsec for the baseline version ($2a = 16 \text{ cm}$, $\lambda_{\text{eff}} = 425 \text{ nm}$).

2.2. Stochastic models of observations

A recording of counts in the time interval $t = 0$ to $t = T$ constitutes an observation, which may be given in form of a step function $N(t) =$ number of counts up to time t . The observation is modelised as a realisation of a Poisson process with intensity function $I(t)$. This means that the probability of getting a count in the interval $[t, t+dt]$ is $I(t)dt$.

When there is only one star in the instantaneous field the intensity function is set as

$$I(t) = A [1 + M f(vt - p)], \quad (1)$$

where $f(x)$ is a known function with period s [e.g. $f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cos(2\pi i x/s)$, where a_i are specified constants] and A , M and p are unknown parameters (average intensity, modulation factor and position of star). The speed of scanning (v) is assumed to be known and constant with time. For any observation $N(t)$ we can get estimates of A , M and p by fitting (1) to the observation.

With two stars in the field (the main star and the parasite) we get an intensity function of the form

$$I(t) = A [1 + M f(vt - p) + m f(vt - p - d)], \quad (2)$$

in which A is the average intensity, M and m are the modulation factors for the main star and the parasite, respectively, p is the position of the main star and d the position of the parasite relative to the main star. As before, A , M , p , m , d can be estimated by fitting (2) to the observation.

The possibility of having more than one parasite within the cathod spot is neglected.

2.3. Procedure for estimating p , the main star's position

In the most frequent case we do not know beforehand if there is a non-negligible parasite in the field or not, and consequently we do not know which intensity function is relevant, (1) or (2). One might think that it would be safe to use (2) in all such cases, with the result $m \approx 0$ and d indeterminate if there were no parasite. However, as will be seen later, the solution for p would also be rather indeterminate, although unbiased, if there were no parasite. Constant use of (1), on the other hand, would always give well-

determined solutions for p , but biased if there were a parasite.

This is naturally regarded as a hypothesis-testing problem. The null-hypothesis H_0 (no parasite) is tested against the alternative hypothesis H_1 (parasite present). Either hypothesis is accepted according to a well-defined criterion whereupon the corresponding intensity function is used to estimate p . The details of this procedure are given in the Appendix. The criterion is a comparison of the goodness of fit obtained with the two intensity functions: only when (2) fits the observation considerably much better than (1) is H_1 accepted.

It is now possible to compute a few functions which are very useful for the optimisation of the grid. They are all functions of the grid period (s), the total number of counts from the main star ($ATc = N(T)c$, where $c = 1/[1 + \text{dex}(-0.4\Delta m)]$ is the fraction of light from the main star), the magnitude difference (Δm) and distance (d) between the two stars. (Of course, d is irrelevant when there is no parasite, $\Delta m = \infty$.) Let X be a vector-valued parameter which contains all these arguments and also A , M , p and m , thus defining the true situation. Furthermore, let $\hat{p}_0$ and $\hat{p}_1$ be the estimates of the true position p obtained when H_0 or H_1 is accepted. We have

$P(X)$ = probability of accepting H_1 when X is the true state,

$b_i(X) = E(\hat{p}_i - p) =$ bias of $\hat{p}_i$, the estimate when H_i is accepted,

$\sigma_i(X) = [E(\hat{p}_i - E\hat{p}_i)^2]^{1/2} =$ mean error of $\hat{p}_i$. ($i = 0, 1$)

The next section gives some numerical results for P , b and σ .

3. Numerical results.

3.1. The mean error of the position of a single star

- Fig. 2 Fig. 2 shows how σ_0 depends on grid period (s) and slit width (r). The value of r giving the smallest mean error σ_0 for each s is shown in
- Fig. 3 Fig. 3 together with the minimum values of σ_0 . In all subsequent computations is r chosen as in Fig. 3. Notice the primary minimum of σ_0 in Fig. 3 for $s = 1.5$ and the 18% higher secondary minimum at $\sigma_0 = 2.6 - 2.9$.

Fig. 2. The mean error σ_0 of a one-coordinate measurement of a star as function of grid period (s) and slit width (r). σ_0 , s and r are in resolution units, σ_0'' and s'' are the mean error and grid period in arcsec for the baseline instrument. The mean error is for a record of 3161(r/s) counts (1^s observation of a 9^m star with the baseline instrument).

Fig. 3. Dashed curve shows the optimum slit width (r_{opt}) as function of grid period (s), the solid curve shows the corresponding mean error σ_0 of a single-star observation. s, r_{opt} and σ_0 are in resolution units.

3.2. The mean error of the position of the main star in presence of a parasite

Fig. 4

σ_1 , the mean error of $\hat{p}_1$, depends on s and d as shown in Fig. 4. The Figure gives the asymptotic mean errors as the magnitude difference Δm increases indefinitely. This should be multiplied approximately by the factor $1 + \text{dex}(-0.4 - 0.4\Delta m)$ or 1.40, 1.16 and 1.06 for $\Delta m = 0, 1$ and 2 . For comparison, the mean error σ_0 of a single-star observation is reproduced from Fig. 3.

Both σ_0 and σ_1 are inversely proportional to the square-root of the number of counts.

The following should be noticed:

- /1/ $s \gtrsim 2$ is required for the solution of p from (2) whereas $s \gtrsim 1$ is sufficient for a single star. This is directly related to the number of Fourier components in the light curve.
- /2/ σ_1 approaches σ_0 for a well-separated pair of stars ($d \approx 1$), but increases indefinitely for $d \rightarrow 0$.
- /3/ The minimum σ_1 occurs for $s = 2.5 - 2.6$ almost independently of d . This nearly coincides with the secondary minimum of σ_0 for $s = 2.6 - 2.9$.

3.3. Detectability and probability of accepting H_1

We can define a quantity Λ , here called detectability, which is directly proportional to the number of counts and can be related to the probability of accepting H_1 as function of the true state parameter X (see Appendix). As a rule of thumb we may say that $\Lambda \gtrsim 8$ means that the probability of detecting the parasite is fairly good ($\gtrsim 0.5$). $\Lambda = 0$ for $d = 0$ or $\Delta m = \infty$.

Fig. 5

Fig. 5 shows $\lg \Lambda$ as a function of s and d for $\Delta m = 1$ and 3161δ counts. Except for separations comparable with $s/2$ there is little dependence of Λ on s for $s \gtrsim 2.5$. In the critical cases when d is small there are flat maxima for $s = 2.6 - 2.8$ and $s = 4.4$.

σ_1

Fig. 4. Mean error σ_1 of the main star's position as function of grid period (s) and distance (d) to the parasite. σ_1 , s and d are in resolution units. The number of counts from the main star is 31618 and the parasite is much fainter than the main star. The mean error σ_0 for a single-star observation (from Fig. 3) is given for comparison.

Fig. 5. Detectability (Λ) of a parasite one magnitude fainter than the main star, as a function of grid period (s) and the distance (d) between the two stars. The number of counts from the main star is 3161δ . s and d are in resolution units, Λ is dimensionless. $\Lambda \gtrsim 8$ is required for a good chance of detecting the parasite (dashed line).

Fig. 6

Because Λ is proportional to the number of counts we can easily compute how many counts are required to separate two stars with a given magnitude difference and angle between them. This is more clearly demonstrated in Fig. 6, which gives the required number of counts $N = ATc$ from the main star as a function of d and Δm , but only for grid period $s = 2.5$. An example: with the baseline instrument, a 9^m star and 4^s integration time, detection requires $d'' > 14, 17, 27$ for $\Delta m = 0, 1, 2$, respectively; for $\Delta m > 2.5$ detection is improbable even with the most favourable separation $d = 0.45$.

3.4. The bias due to an undetected parasite

Fig. 7

Fig. 7 shows b_0 (the bias of $\hat{p}_0$) as a function of d and Δm for $s = 2.5$. In the example above we find that the detection limits correspond to the biases $0.070, 0.047$ and 0.025 for $\Delta m = 0, 1$ and 2 .

The bias at the detection limit (or the maximum bias if detection is impossible) represents the worst case when there is a parasite with given Δm . As a typical bias for a given Δm we may take the rms expected bias, computed according to

$$b_{\text{rms}}^2 = \langle (1 - P)b_0^2 + P b_1^2 \rangle \quad (\text{averaged over all values of } d) \quad (3)$$

Table 1

where P is the probability of detection, b_0 the bias if the parasite is undetected (probability $1 - P$) and $b_1 = 0$ is the bias if the parasite is detected (probability P). Table 1 gives b_{rms} for $\Delta m = 0 - 4$ and a few different apertures, computed for a 4^s observation of a 9^m star. The biases with $s = 1.5$ RU and $s = 2.5$ RU are compared. The table also gives the a priori probability of getting a parasite in the field. In about 14 % of the observations there will be a parasite (almost always a physical companion to the main star) brighter than $\Delta m = 2.5$. In all these cases will the longer grid period (2.5 RU) give a substantial reduction of b_{rms} .

4. Conclusions

The numerical results presented here all refer to an instrument with a diffraction pattern like the dashed curve in Fig. 1. It seems that the secondary minimum of the single-star accuracy (σ_0 , Fig. 3), the minimum of σ_1 (Fig. 4) and the maximum of detectability (Fig. 5) at about $s = 2.5 - 2.8$ RU can all be traced back to the shape of the

diffraction pattern. In this case there is no serious conflict between the demands for high single-star accuracy and good detectability, once we have been convinced by the statistics of double-star companions that we cannot ignore parasites completely.

The situation may be different, however, if we have another aperture shape and/or optical aberrations. The optimisation of the grid and the computation of the distribution of observational errors could be more generally tackled as a problem in decision theory. The present note should therefore be considered as a very preliminary and simplified study of the problem.

Table 1. The expected rms bias of the position of a 9^m star from a 4^s observation when there is a parasite of magnitude $9 + \Delta m$ somewhere in the field. The pairs of numbers are b_{rms} for $s = 1.5$ RU (above) and $s = 2.5$ RU (below) in milliarcsec. Also given are preliminary estimates of the probability of getting a parasite of given magnitude within the $30'' \times 30''$ cathod spot. $P(\text{chance})$ is the probability averaged over the sky of a parasite which is not physically connected with the main star; $P(\text{comp})$ is the probability for a physical companion to the main star with $0.1'' \leq d'' \leq 15''$.

Aperture 2a x b (cm ²)	Δm					
	0	1	2	3	4	
16 x 8	119	38	15	6	2.3	(baseline)
	20	14	11	6	2.5	
24 x 8	79	25	10	4	1.5	
	11	8	6	4	1.7	
32 x 8	59	19	7	3	1.2	
	7	5	4	3	1.3	
16 x 16	119	38	15	6	2.3	
	14	11	8	6	2.5	
P(chance)	.00022	.00058	.0016	.0040	.010	
P(comp)	.03	.06	.05	.05	.05	

Fig. 6. The required number of counts (N) from the main star for a good chance to detect a parasite which is Δm magnitudes fainter, as a function of the angle (d) between the two stars. d'' is the angle in arcsec for the baseline instrument and T is the necessary integration time for a 9^{m} star observed with the baseline instrument. The grid period is $s = 2.5$ RU.

Fig. 7. The positional error (bias b_0) caused by an undetected parasite at distance d from the main star and Δm magnitudes fainter. The grid period $s = 2.5 \text{ RU} = 1''.4$ for the baseline instrument.

Appendix

A mathematical formulation of the detection problem

The configuration of two stars may be characterised by the vector $\Theta = (A, M, p, m, d)$ belonging to the parameter space Ω . A subset ω of Ω contains the parameters corresponding to cases when there is no parasite (e.g., $m = d = 0$). Thus $\Theta \in \omega$ means that we have a single star and $\Theta \in \Omega - \omega$ means that there is a parasite.

For a given observation $\{N(t); 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ we have to test the hypothesis $H_0: \Theta \in \omega$ against the hypothesis $H_1: \Theta \in \Omega - \omega$. This is made by fitting an intensity function $I(t; \Theta)$, parametrised by Θ , to the observation under the two restrictions $\Theta \in \omega$ and $\Theta \in \Omega - \omega$. This leads to the two estimates $\hat{\Theta}_0$ and $\hat{\Theta}_1$ of the true parameter Θ . By comparing the goodness of fit for the two cases, one of the hypotheses is accepted and the corresponding estimate adopted.

We have

$$I(t; \Theta) = A \left[1 + M f(vt - p) + m f(vt - p - d) \right], \quad (A1)$$

where $f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \cos(2\pi i x/s)$ and v is known. A maximum likelihood estimator can be used for fitting I to the observation. If $\{N(t); 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ is a realisation of a Poisson process with intensity function $I(t; \Theta)$ we get the likelihood function

$$\begin{aligned} \text{lik}(\Theta) &= \text{pr} \left[N(t); 0 \leq t \leq T \mid \Theta \right] = \\ &= \exp \left\{ - \int_0^T I(t; \Theta) dt + \int_0^T \ln [I(t; \Theta)] dN(t) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (A2)$$

The estimates $\hat{\Theta}_i$, $i = 0, 1$ satisfy $\text{lik}(\hat{\Theta}_0) = \sup_{\omega} \text{lik}(\Theta)$ and $\text{lik}(\hat{\Theta}_1) = \sup_{\Omega - \omega} \text{lik}(\Theta)$.

Under the correct hypothesis the maximum likelihood estimate is asymptotically unbiased and the error covariance matrix can be estimated as the inverse of the Fisher information matrix

$$F(\theta) = \int_0^T \left[\frac{\partial I(t; \theta)}{\partial \theta} \right] \left[\frac{\partial I(t; \theta)}{\partial \theta} \right]^t \frac{dt}{I(t; \theta)}. \quad (A3)$$

$F(\theta)$ is a 3×3 diagonal matrix when H_0 is true and in this case the expression for the mean error of $\hat{p}$ will be the same as derived in the note 77-03-10. But when H_1 is true $F(\theta)$ is a 5×5 matrix with non-zero off-diagonal elements and must be inverted to give σ_1 .

The bias of the solution $\hat{\theta}_0$ in case H_1 is true is estimated by fitting $I(t; \theta \in \omega)$ to the true intensity function, i.e. by maximising

$$\int_0^T \ln \left[I(t; \theta \in \omega) \right] I(t; \theta_{\text{true}}) dt.$$

The likelihood of an estimate, $\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_1)$, is by itself a good measure of goodness of fit. We generally have $\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_1) > \text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_0)$ because even if there is no parasite in the field we can probably get a slightly better fit by assuming that there is one. Therefore we cannot simply choose the hypothesis giving the greater likelihood, but we rather apply the likelihood-ratio test

$$\frac{\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_0)}{\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_1)} < C \Leftrightarrow \text{accept } H_1 \quad (A4)$$

C is a pre-assigned value between 0 and 1.

The statistic

$$W = -2 \ln \left[\frac{\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_0)}{\text{lik}(\hat{\theta}_1)} \right] = -2 \int_0^T \ln \left[\frac{I(t; \hat{\theta}_0)}{I(t; \hat{\theta}_1)} \right] dN(t) \quad (A5)$$

has asymptotically the non-central chi-square distribution with $\dim(\Omega) - \dim(\omega) = 2$ degrees of freedom and non-centrality parameter

$$\Lambda = -2 \int_0^T \ln \frac{I(t; E\hat{\theta}_0)}{I(t; E\hat{\theta}_1)} I(t; \theta_{\text{true}}) dt. \quad (A6)$$

The cumulative distribution of W is then

$$\text{pr} [W > W' | \Lambda] = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (\Lambda/2)^j \exp(-\Lambda/2)/j! \cdot \sum_{i=0}^j (W'/2)^i \exp(-W'/2)/i! \quad (\text{A7})$$

When H_0 is true ($\Lambda = 0$) this reduces to the ordinary (central) chi-square distribution with two degrees of freedom

$$\text{pr} [W > W' | \Lambda = 0] = \exp(-W'/2). \quad (\text{A8})$$

The likelihood-ratio criterion (A4) for accepting H_1 is equivalently written $W > -2\ln C$. Comparison with (A8) shows that C is the probability of 'false alarm', i.e. of accepting H_1 when H_0 is true. It is desirable to keep this probability at a reasonably low level, say $C = 0.01$, or $-2\ln C \approx 9$. The non-central chi-square distribution is such that $\text{pr} [W > W' | \Lambda] > 0.5$ for $\Lambda \gtrsim W' - 1$, when W' is not too small. Thus, for a good chance of detecting a parasite we must have $\Lambda \gtrsim 8$. This is not very sensitive to a change of C ; $C = 0.1$ and 0.001 correspond to the detection limits $\Lambda \gtrsim 3.6$ and 13 . However, the numerical results in Fig. 6 and Table 1 have been computed with $C = 0.01$. The non-centrality parameter Λ is called 'detectability' in this note because it is a direct measure of the inconsistency between the true light curve and the best-fitting single-star light curve. As seen from (A6) Λ increases in direct proportion to T and I , i.e. to the total number of counts.